

Emotional Intelligence or Artificial Intelligence for salespeople: An exploratory study among sales managers

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Conflit d'intérêts : L'auteur ne signale aucun conflit d'intérêts.

Pour citer cet article : OUAZZANI TOUHAMI, I. & AZOUAOUI, H (2022) « Emotional Intelligence or Artificial Intelligence for salespeople: An exploratory study among sales managers » , African Scientific Journal « Volume 03, Numéro 12 » pp: 477-493.

Date de soumission : Mai 2022

Date de publication : Juin 2022

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.6907157
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Abstract

Artificial intelligence is one of the most powerful technologies that the world has ever seen. Many salespeople fear being replaced by robots even if they have developed soft skills like emotional intelligence.

Through this study, we try to understand if artificial intelligence will replace emotional intelligence which is considered an essential skill for salespeople. To do so, we conducted a qualitative approach using a semi-structured interview with 10 sales managers who work in the different B2B sectors.

To analyze our data, we use thematic analysis and content analysis. The results of our study showed that Moroccan companies use artificial intelligence to digitalize some tasks and should collaborate with machines to succeed. Our study shows the importance of ethics in using artificial intelligence.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence- Emotional Intelligence – Salespeople– Sales industry

1. Introduction

If we had the opportunity to learn one lesson from the Covid-19 pandemic, it is that the world can change overnight. Employees working in sales industries were afraid of losing their jobs not because of the pandemic. But because of the power of artificial intelligence can significantly impact their work. Some salespeople even chose to leave their careers and start new adventures. The most resilient ones have begun training on the side of their work to follow the market trend. Artificial intelligence interprets external data, learns from that data, and uses that knowledge to achieve specific goals through flexible adaptation (Haenlein & Andreas, 2019). It allows learning from the experience and helps to eliminate ordinary tasks and focus on more significant tasks (Morikawa, 2017).

Pioneer industries are the source of many patents. IBM is considered one of the leader companies in B2b sales (Gross et al., 2021). In the 30s, IBM revolutionized the sales field by recruiting high profiles. Nowadays, the company started using artificial intelligence applications and solutions to manage their business portfolio and answer questions in a natural way (IBM, 2021).

Having the latest technology in artificial intelligence is not enough. To succeed in sales, salespeople need some skills to perform in their daily. Emotional intelligence is one of them that makes salespeople understand their customers' needs (Fatt, 2002).

Emotional intelligence also helps salespeople to have strong relationships and achieve sales performance (AIDosiry et al., 2015). But even if salespeople can manage their emotions, they will always be afraid of the powerful software that can do the same tasks as them and achieve operational efficiency (Russell, et al., 2015).

Many studies showed the link between emotional intelligence and other aspects. Few of the studies tried to understand how artificial intelligence will replace emotional intelligence for salespeople.

Through this study, we will understand if the emotional intelligence of salespeople will be replaced by artificial intelligence technology. To answer this question, we will present a literature review on emotional intelligence and then the relationship between emotional intelligence and artificial intelligence for salespeople. In what relates to methodology, we will conduct a qualitative study based on an interview with 10 Moroccan B2B sales directors to get their perceptions about this subject.

And then we will present the result of this study that will help us to understand the degree of integration of artificial intelligence in the different sales industries and how this technology will help salespeople in their emotional work.

2. Literature review

2.1 Emotional Intelligence

Rational intelligence was considered the only type of intelligence a person could have. However, Emotions disrupt our daily life until the day that Thorndike proposed the theory of social intelligence, which assumes the existence of three types of intelligence (Thorndike & Stein, 1937).

The theory of multiple intelligence developed by (Gardner, 1983) suggests the presence of seven types of intelligence. Among these types, we find intrapersonal and interpersonal intelligence, considered to be antecedents of emotional intelligence.

The first scientific publication on emotional intelligence was (Salovey & Mayer, 1990). They define emotional intelligence as *"the ability to monitor one's own and others' feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them and to use this information to guide one's thinking and actions the ability to monitor one's own and others' feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them and to use this information to guide one's thinking and actions."* The general public know emotional intelligence through the publication of the book "Emotional intelligence: Why it can matter more than IQ?" (Goleman, 1996). The latest version of the model includes: (self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship management) (Goleman, 2017).

Several authors propose models of emotional intelligence with scales that can measure it. These authors also tried to measure the impact of emotional intelligence on several variables such as work performance (Druskat et al., 2005), team performance ((Feyerherm & Rice, 2002), and group cohesion (Moore & Mamiseishvili, 2012).

In sales literature, numerous studies show that emotional intelligence skill is essential to business success (Webb, 2011). Salespeople need a high emotional intelligence level to build quality customer relationships. They also need to be more aware of using artificial intelligence to understand their customers' emotions.

2.2 Emotional Intelligence and Artificial intelligence

To understand the issue, the theory of Task-technology fit (TTF), (Goodhue & Thompson, 1995), an approach that explains why salespeople should use technology to achieve performance. Salespeople need to be more resilient in using new technologies. Several types of research show that artificial intelligence is bringing significant changes to human work (Larivière et al., 2017).

Since 1950, some authors explained how machines will be more powerful than humans and can even replace them in few year (Turing, 1950). Other reports show that artificial intelligence will cause a 5% loss of jobs (Manyika et al., 2017). In Morocco and during a conference organized by CDG on the impact of artificial intelligence on jobs, several speakers confirmed that artificial intelligence would bring a profound transformation (Challange, 2021).

In other words, artificial intelligence is understanding structured and unstructured data (Luo et al., 2022). If statistics are based on deduction (Teboul, 2018), artificial intelligence is based on inference and induction. More than 80% of the Internet's data is unstructured (Rizkallah, 2017). This technology allows learning from experiences (Marr, 2018). That is why the data processing is done in a sophisticated way. It allows to detect the keywords, understand people's emotions, and offer suggestions that will meet their needs (Paschen et al., 2020). But recently, findings have shown the opposite. Machines can be mistaken and the crash of two plans leading to one of the biggest catastrophes is the most reliable example.

Other studies explained that artificial intelligence tools (Chui, et al., 2015) and how they can replace some tasks of salespeople. In their research (Huang & Rust, 2020) propose a classification of different levels of intelligence from mechanical intelligence, which is routine tasks that can easily imitate, to empathic intelligence, which is based on emotions and is very difficult to replace.

Empathic intelligence is one of the branches of the emotional intelligence model developed by (Goleman, 1995). He defines emotional intelligence as the ability to recognize and understand the emotions of others to interact with them (Goleman, 1996). The particularity of emotional intelligence is that we can't measure our emotions. For the specialists in artificial intelligence, we can calculate emotions by using algorithms (Minsky, 2006).

Economic Forum World considered emotional intelligence one of the essential skills to develop in order to stand out in the professional world (Licheva, 2020). Emotional intelligence predicts success better than Quotient Intelligent QI (Bar-On, 2006) and contributes to the success and

achievement of people at work (Goleman, 1995). To sum up, Emotional intelligence is essential in a context where human interactions are the center of exchanges (Prentice, et al., 2019).

In the sales literature, Emotional intelligence helps salespeople stand out and perform well (Kadic-Maglajlic et al., 2016). There are other classifications that explain how some levels of artificial intelligence can surpass humans. Strong artificial intelligence (Wirth, 2018) is a form of intelligence capable of reasoning better than humans. We also find that super artificial intelligence can have creativity and other social skills (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2019). The work of (Manyika et al., 2015) shows that artificial intelligence will not be able to replace all jobs at once.

Artificial intelligence will start by removing mechanical tasks and can also replace some heterogeneous functions by trying to decompensate and replace them. It can be used to automate specific routine tasks for salespeople (Salesforce, 2017). Salesforce company uses artificial intelligence in CRM Data to achieve better customer results. Some companies use artificial intelligence to train their salesforce (Honeycutt et al., 2002). For example, the company ZOOM uses Chorus software to offer training for its sales force (Matheny, 2019). Startups have created personalized training. Insideboard has begun with two models which are Insideboard Discovery Day and Sales enablement day (Insideboard, 2022).

The company Metlife used Cogito software to analyze the conversation between salespeople and customers and provide feedback on the sales exchange (Council, 2019). However, this software has not had the social skills to communicate its input appropriately to salespeople (Shellenbarger, 2019).

Some software can understand the words spoken by customers and give them the answer according to their emotions (González-Rodríguez et al., 2020). A study by (Henkel et al., 2019) has shown that using artificial intelligence to recognize feelings can help to regulate emotions by employees and reduce stress.

3. Methodology

Qualitative study is used to understand the perceptions of the respondents and their experiences. In our study we aren't looking for general information (Hammarberg et al., 2016), but to see the characteristics of each sector that is way the qualitative study is more coherent with our research question.

The objective of this study is to understand how artificial intelligence will replace the emotional intelligence of salespeople. To answer this problem, we set up qualitative research that can provide exciting results if treated correctly (Bazeley, 2009). In this study, we chose semi-directive interviews using an interview guide based on the literature review with eight sales directors. Our guide is based on questions related to three themes:

- 1 The concept of artificial intelligence in sales industries in Morocco;
- 2 The practices of artificial intelligence already exist in the sales industry;
- 3 The influence that artificial intelligence has on the emotional work of salespeople.

We targeted these people using social networks (Instagram and LinkedIn). The two people contacted via Instagram are public figures who use the social network for professional purposes. The two people contacted via Instagram responded positively to our request. As for LinkedIn, out of 14 people, we had four responses. The participants in this study came from different activity sectors, which is our study's purpose. We selected only one interviewee for each field of action because our objective is to understand what happens in every sector of activity.

During the interviews, the participants were open to expressing their opinions freely. To analyze the results, we chose thematic analysis to find the common thread in all interviews (DeSantis & Ugarriza, 2000), and content analysis to analyze our data which describes and not measures (Forman, & Damschroder., 2007). The fact of combining these two techniques of the analysis makes it possible to answer the questioning of the people compared to an event (Ayres, 2007) which goes perfectly with our research question.

Figure N°1: Characteristics of our sample

Interviewee	Gender	Post occupied	Experience	Sector
Interviewee 1	Female	Sales director	5	Automotive
Interviewee 2	Male	Sales director	22	Telecom
Interviewee 3	Male	Sales director	20	Pharmaceutical
Interviewee 4	Male	Sales director	10	Agri-food
Interviewee 5	Female	Sales director	17	Industrial
Interviewee 6	Male	Sales director	20	Banking
Interviewee 7	Male	Sales director	15	Insurance
Interviewee 8	Male	Sales director	16	Outsourcing
Interviewee 9	Female	Sales director	10	Services
Interviewee 10	Female	Sales director	7	Agricultural

Source: Author's processing.

4. Results of the study

4.1 Digitalization of some tasks

The work of salespeople is composed of a set of tasks. Some tasks are essential to increase the salesperson's performance; other tasks can be trivial. During the interviews, the respondents affirmed that their companies have started using digital solutions to make the work of salespeople much more efficient.

Salespeople use CRM to help them recognize their customers' needs. Those CRMs are equipped with artificial intelligence to facilitate data understanding and interpretation (Chatterjee et al., 2021). The Digitalization of tasks consists in using social networks to interact with customers in the different stages of the sales process, from the prospecting of new customers to customer management, as proposed by (Dubinsky, 1981).

Interviewee 4 confided that *"Digitalization of databases, commercial CRM that we have set up which allows better customer portfolio management. Today, many companies use archaic tools that are obsolete with Excel files. The salesperson deals with humans 100% of the time, and the tool is a back-office procedure since the need to train these people in emotional intelligence"*.

Interviewee 5 said, *"We can digitize tasks such as sending emails, tasks that will not affect the success of the sale process because in b2b is not like e-commerce sites where you have less human contact"*.

Interviewee 10 said, *"We use social networks for prospecting; even though our salespeople are present online, they must-have skills that will allow them to better interact with their customers on these networks."*

The digitization of specific tasks can benefit salespeople and the organization because it will help achieve a competitive advantage (Leeflang et al., 2013). Artificial intelligence can be beneficial in removing some tasks and letting salespeople focus on jobs that will generate value. It can also help salespeople achieve sales performance (Ferreira et al., 2020). It will automate tasks such as sending order validation emails and let salespeople focus on negotiation.

4.2 Human-machine collaboration

All the people we interviewed confirmed that artificial intelligence could not replace the emotional intelligence of salespeople. Sales jobs are based on the interaction between people;

without this interaction, we cannot make exchanges in B2B sales. The interviewees were all interested in the importance of artificial intelligence tools to facilitate the work of salespeople. Interviewee 2 said, *"I don't know if there is software that can develop the intuitive side of things that we humans have developed. At the logical level, yes, this software will have to help humans understand what is happening around them and not replace them"*.

Interviewee 3 said, *"We receive offers from companies that propose applications to take online orders. We tried those applications during the period of Covid 19, but it does not work... what we need are solutions that will help us understand our customer's need"*.

The 4th industrial revolution is based on replacing employees with machines to obtain results. On the other hand, the 5th industrial revolution implies that humans and machines must work together, building on each other's strengths to achieve good results for all parties (Noble et al., 2022). Artificial intelligence will help salespeople better to understand the behaviors and motivations of their customers, and employees can distinguish themselves by the social skills that will allow them to interact efficiently.

Artificial intelligence or any advanced technology can only serve the salesperson to provide relevant solutions for their customers. After a long series of study that shows the importance of technology, we are now more interested in a new era that we should use marketing 5.0 to humanity's causes.

4.3 The importance of ethics in using artificial intelligence

A set of values must accompany the use of artificial intelligence to organize these different tools better. Several of our respondents explained that they could not use artificial intelligence to discriminate between salespeople. Artificial intelligence must include many regulations to be used for good purposes.

Interviewee 6 said, *"You just have to know how to use artificial intelligence tools for good causes."*

Interviewee 5 said, *"Some company uses artificial intelligence to manipulate their customers, and this is not our objective. We are looking to build a solid relationship with our partners"*.

We can use artificial intelligence to manipulate the vulnerable emotional state of customers (Petropoulos 2022). In principle, companies use sophisticated software to predict their customers' behavior, but they can use it for their employees to maximize value.

IT companies should respect ethical rules when integrating artificial intelligence into applications or platforms. Those regulations should start from training their engineers to developing software that incorporates artificial intelligence (Madiega, 2019). B2B buyers and all the managers engaged in the purchasing process should acquire solutions that respect the ethical rules for salespeople.

Our study tries to understand if artificial intelligence will replace emotional intelligence but this study explains to us the state of artificial intelligence in B2B sales. None of the respondents explained that artificial intelligence could replace salespeople in executing their daily tasks, like understanding the regulation of emotions which are branches of emotional intelligence. Our respondents said that some software could understand the emotions of b2b customers, and others can interpret emotions in the images. Still, they cannot develop the emotional intelligence wish is a competence that humans have created.

5. Discussion

Artificial intelligence started by replacing mechanical tasks before returning to empathic intelligence (Huang and al 2018). For the automotive sector, artificial intelligence will automate tasks for workers but not for salespeople.

Our study aimed to understand how artificial intelligence is going to replace the emotional intelligence of salespeople in the Moroccan context. We interviewed sales managers to understand the specificity of different industries. The results of our study allowed to conclude that artificial intelligence will not replace the emotional intelligence of salespeople.

This study brings answers to understand what it is happening in the different sectors of B2B sales. Our interviews show that artificial intelligence tools are much more present in the industrial and service industries. This is mainly because the education level or market requirements are much more critical than in other sectors. The conception of these tools must be customized to understand the specifics of each industry. They should be designed quickly with a 3-win perspective to satisfy all parties. For companies, it must allow them to reduce additional costs and invest in other value-generating activities. Artificial intelligence software should provide a unique and personalized user experience, and for salespeople, it will help to cover other markets.

All the statements our interviewees made align with what we have found in the literature. A study by (Morikawa, 2017) shows that artificial intelligence will remove mundane work and

help high-level jobs to complete their essential tasks. Digitalization will allow companies to save time and reinvest it in other activities that generate value (Lawrance and al 2019).

For the sectors that replaced salespeople with applications to take orders during the Covid pandemic, the failure is mainly due to the obligation to integrate the social distinction in there. Applications. The decision to incorporate those types of software must follow a strategy and allocate a budget to train salespeople and show them to help them do their jobs well.

Morocco is integrating technology into different national strategies. In what concerns artificial intelligence, the kingdom has aligned to various recommendations dictated by UNESCO, which aims to regulate the use of artificial intelligence for causes that will serve humanity. Those recommendations should support the protection of the massive development of human-centered applications (Madiega, 2019).

6. Managerial implications

Moroccan companies now use CRM and other tools to help them understand their customer's needs. B2B sales companies must be more resilient to use new technology because it will serve them to achieve sales performance. It is crucial to allocate a budget in order to raise awareness in all parts of the company and train its sales force to use artificial intelligence tools.

Salespeople should not be afraid of using artificial intelligence because it will help them in their daily tasks. Several studies have shown that people with a higher level of emotional intelligence are resilient (Schneider et al., 2013). But for people that have a low level of emotional intelligence will face difficulties in assuming the importance of artificial intelligence. So, it is essential to design a customized in order to help them to use it.

Moreover, we suggest that Moroccan Companies invest in sophisticated solutions that integrate a high level of artificial intelligence. They should not follow the same artificial intelligence process sequentially but invest in strong and weak artificial intelligence.

Finally, we propose to create a database which salespeople will collect. Salespeople will describe the emotional state of their customers in the database, and they will use it to predict the dynamic behavior of customers to provide an emotional response according to their personality type.

Conclusion

Many studies try to explain the link between artificial intelligence and another variable.

The particularity of this study is to show the importance of salespeople's artificial intelligence and emotional intelligence.

Emotional intelligence is one of the essential skills in the sales profession, and the integration of artificial intelligence can only help salespeople understand customers', needs and bring them relevant solutions. On the emotional level, the integration of artificial intelligence can only be beneficial if used for a good cause. B2B sales company in Morocco uses artificial intelligence to digitalize some tasks for their salesforce and make the work easier.

Future research should take into consideration some limitations of our study. First, our qualitative research should consider the opinion of salespeople to know their perceptions on the subject through a focus group. In our case, it was not possible because we had to relaunch some of our interviews.

Second, a quantitative study should have been a plus to generalize this study to a vast population. Finally, this study will be interesting if have chosen only one sector because the result will be more specific.

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